

A Counter-Example-Driven Approach to the Synthesis of Synchronization Code for Distributed Algorithms

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Abstract. We present an approach to automatically synthesize synchronization code for distributed programs, assuming a multi-thread shared-variables model of computation. Our approach takes as input the global properties to be satisfied, and a collection of local process specifications, expressed in First-Order Relational Logic. A SAT solver is used to enumerate potential implementations of the (local) processes, and then a model checker is used to verify if their concurrent composition satisfies the required global properties. Whether this is the case, valid synchronization code is obtained; otherwise, a counterexample is produced. These counterexamples can then be used to guide our SAT-based search, by incrementally refining the local process implementations. We show that our approach is correct and complete, under a given bound on the size of the process implementations, and applies to general LTL formulas. We developed a prototype of our approach and applied it to well-known case studies of distributed algorithms.

1 Introduction

Distributed algorithms are an interesting kind of concurrent programs, successfully used in modern software developments, such as cryptocurrencies and web-based collaborative applications. An interesting characteristic of distributed algorithms is that they lack of a centralised control, and therefore they usually exhibit a high degree of fault-tolerance. But at the same time, the inherent concurrency of distributed programs introduces subtle challenges to deal with during the development and verification of such kind of systems. Typical problems in concurrency are given by *race conditions* and *deadlocks* [1, 2]. Thus, the development of distributed code usually demands the correct use of *synchronization primitives*, such as semaphores, locks and monitors, to organise the access to shared resources and avoid deadlocks. However, the correct use of these primitives is one of the most challenging tasks for programmers.

Interestingly, important properties of concurrent and distributed programs, e.g., deadlock freedom or mutual exclusion, can be expressed in temporal logics

[3]. This makes these kinds of programs particularly suitable for program synthesis. However, the synthesis of distributed algorithms is a complex problem, indeed it is undecidable in many cases [4]. In this paper, we propose a bounded synthesis technique for automatically generating synchronization code for distributed programs, it uses modular specifications and local reasoning (at the process level) to avoid the explicit construction of the space of global states. The technique uses SAT solving to construct process candidates and symbolic model checking to refine these candidates. Process specifications are written in First-Order Relational Logic (FORL), an extension of First-Order Logic capable of expressing temporal properties, which is the basis of modern specification languages [5, 6].

Precisely, our approach takes as inputs a collection S_0, \dots, S_n of process specifications, which are given in terms of FORL theories. Communication between the processes is achieved by means of shared variables, which is formally captured as symbol sharing between the theories. Furthermore, a global temporal property ϕ is considered to describe a goal that the composition of processes to be synthesized must satisfy. From these specifications, our technique attempts to construct process implementations P_0, \dots, P_n , satisfying the corresponding “local” process specifications (i.e., $P_i \models S_i$), such that their interleaved concurrent execution satisfy ϕ (i.e., $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n \models \phi$). We assume an asynchronous shared-memory model of concurrency, which is common in modern multicore processors and object-oriented languages such as `Java`, `Python` or `C#`. Our approach uses SAT solving (specifically, the Alloy Analyzer [5]) for checking if the local specification S_i is satisfiable, under a given bound, and when this is the case, the instance produced is used for building the corresponding correct local implementation P_i . Afterwards, our approach uses symbolic model checking for verifying $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n \models \phi$. If the answer is affirmative, then a synchronization code has been found, that guarantees the satisfaction of both, local and global, properties. Otherwise, the produced counterexample is exploited in such a way that the process specifications are refined to improve the SAT-based search for the process implementations. We show that our approach is correct and bounded-complete, i.e., it is guaranteed that, if there exists a valid synchronization code within the given bound, the technique will be able to find it.

In summary, the contributions of this paper are:

- A formal characterization of asynchronous shared-variables concurrent programs which use locks for synchronization. This framework makes possible modular reasoning over concurrent programs.
- A synthesis algorithm for generating distributed programs from specifications. This procedure avoids the explicit construction of the global state space and uses counterexamples to speed up the synthesis process. It supports both, safety and liveness properties.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Related work is discussed in Section 2, preliminary concepts are revisited in Section 3. Section 4 introduces our model of concurrency and the formalism used to write specifications. The

synthesis algorithm is introduced in Section 5 and the experimental results are presented in Section 6. The proofs of the theorems are gathered in the Appendix.

2 Related Work

The seminal paper of [8] is based on the use of tableau methods for synthesizing synchronization skeletons from global specifications expressed in CTL. Due to scalability reasons, this is impractical for most examples. To avoid the construction of the global state transition system, the work in [9] requires a specification that describes the interaction between each pair of processes, allowing the synthesis method to explore different syntactical combinations with the aim of producing the program. However, no prototype tool is available and the pair-specifications have to be provided by the user. An algorithm for producing Java synchronization code from temporal specifications is presented in [10]. There, processes are described by state machines, its application is restricted to a fragment of CTL, and it synthesizes the global transition system. On the other hand, our approach employs a more declarative specification language (pre-post conditions and invariants), similar to modern languages to specify code (e.g., `Spec#` [11] or `JML` [12]). In addition, our approach applies to general LTL-X specifications, and performs a modular search, based on efficient SAT solving and symbolic model checking techniques, to deal with the state explosion problem.

Counterexample-driven guided inductive synthesis (CEGIS) [13] is directly related with our work. CEGIS reduces the problem of finding a program P to solve the following formula: $\forall x : \sigma(P, x)$, where σ is a program specification and x represents inputs of that program. Inductive generalization is used for generating a candidate solution that initially works for a restricted set of inputs, and then its validity is checked with a verifier (e.g. a model checker). If a counterexample is generated, it is used to refine the restricted sets of inputs. This process is repeated until either, a solution or a negative answer, is returned. The extension of `Alloy`, called `Alloy*` [14], supports higher-order formulas and implements a general version of CEGIS, that might be suitable to solve synthesis problems. In contrast to CEGIS, our approach starts from “loose” versions of the processes whose non-determinism is refined until a solution is obtained. This allows us to “accumulate” counterexamples which can be used throughout all the synthesis process. As noted in [15], it is not direct to use executions of asynchronous concurrent programs as counterexamples in standard CEGIS. Furthermore, CEGIS approaches usually return one solution; our procedure is able to produce all the solutions for a given specification (although this could be very inefficient).

`Sketch` [16, 15] is a synthesizer that uses CEGIS to obtain code from sketched code (i.e., code with “holes”). In `Sketch`, the specifications are given in terms of code containing undefined parts (“holes”), in contrast to our specifications that are more declarative, given in terms of collections of formulas. More importantly, `Sketch` is only able to handle safety properties, while our approach is able to analyse any LTL property. Another important difference is how counterexamples

are processed, in our approach global counterexamples are projected into local executions and then each process is refined using this information, Sketch uses the global counterexamples as observations to perform inductive generalization.

Other works, such as [17, 18], consider only safety properties or are designed for specific problems of programming languages. Another related line of work is that of controller synthesis [4]. This research focuses on open systems (where the environmental actions are not restricted), and the obtained programs are centralized algorithms. An interesting stream of research is the synthesis of distributed open systems [19]. In these works the architecture of the system is given as a graph, and the procedure also synthesizes a configuration of the graph when possible. This is a more general problem compared to the one considered here, and these kinds of problems are undecidable in many cases. Lazy synthesis [20] proposes a similar method to the one presented here: an SMT solver is used to obtain processes, then a bounded model checker is used to obtain processes from the analysis of counterexamples. However, that work focuses on synthesizing reactive controllers, and it is also assumed that a part of the system is given.

3 Preliminaries

Linear Temporal Logic (LTL). LTL has been successfully use to specify temporal properties of concurrent and reactive systems [3]. Let AP be a set of atomic propositions, the syntax of LTL is defined, using the standard logical and temporal operators, by the following grammar: $\Phi ::= p \mid \neg\Phi \mid \Phi \vee \Phi \mid \bigcirc\Phi \mid \Phi\mathbf{U}\Phi$, where $p \in AP$. We additionally consider the usual definitions for *true*, *false*, $\diamond\phi$, $\square\phi$ and $\phi\mathbf{W}\psi$. LTL formulas are interpreted over infinite sequences of the style $\pi = \sigma_0\sigma_1\sigma_2 \dots \in (2^{AP})^\omega$ via a relation of satisfaction \models , defined recursively as follows:

- $\sigma \models p$ iff $p \in \sigma_i$,
- $\sigma \models \phi \vee \psi$ iff $\sigma \models \phi$ or $\sigma \models \psi$
- $\sigma \models \bigcirc\phi$ iff $\sigma_1\sigma_2 \dots \models \phi$
- $\sigma \models \phi\mathbf{U}\psi$ iff $\exists k \leq 0 : \sigma_k\sigma_{k_1} \dots \models \psi$ and $\forall i < k : \sigma_i\sigma_{i+1} \dots \models \phi$.

LTL-X [21] is the fragment of LTL obtained by omitting operator \bigcirc , typically used for expressing LTL stutter invariant properties on concurrent systems [22]. We employ LTL-X to specify the global properties to be satisfied by the system.

Labelled Transition Systems (LTS). The implementations synthesized for processes, will be interpreted as *labelled transition systems*. An LTS $TS = \langle S, Act, \rightarrow, s, AP, L \rangle$ is a tuple, where: S is a (finite) non-empty set of states, Act is a set of actions, $\rightarrow \subseteq S \times Act \times S$ is a labeled transition relation, $s \in S$ is the initial state, AP is a collection of atomic propositions and $L : S \rightarrow 2^{AP}$ a labelling function. For the sake of simplicity, we write $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ instead of $\langle s, a, s' \rangle \in \rightarrow$ and $s \rightarrow s'$ when $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ for some $a \in Act$. Also, when convenient, we use the notation $L(s)(x)$ for stating that $x \in L(s)$. A path over a transition system is a (possibly infinite) sequence s_0, s_1, \dots of states such that $\forall i : s_i \rightarrow s_{i+1}$. We say that a path is an *execution* if it is maximal. W.l.o.g., we assume that each state has at

least one successor. The set of all the executions of TS is denoted $Tr(TS)$. Given a LTL formula, we say that an execution $s_0, s_1, \dots \models \phi$ iff $L(s_0), L(s_1), \dots \models \phi$; and we say that $TS \models \phi$ iff $\forall \sigma \in Tr(TS), \sigma \models \phi$. When useful we also consider a relation \models_f which is the restriction of \models to the set of fair executions over TS .

First-Order Relational Logic (FORL). Each process specification will be translated into a set of FORL constraints, in order to use a constraint solver, namely the Alloy Analyzer [5], to build satisfying instances that will be mapped to process implementations. FORL combines first-order sorted logic with relational calculus, it is the basis of modern formal notations such as Alloy [5] and NitPick [6, 23]. FORL formulas may contain quantifiers (\forall and \exists) and boolean operators ($\wedge, \vee, \neg, \Rightarrow$) applied to relational expressions. The expressions are formed by using standard set operators (\cup, \cap, \setminus and \subseteq), and relational expressions: \cdot is the relational join (used for navigating relations), \sim is the relational transpose, $*$ and $+$ are the reflexive and transitive *closures* and $r[s]$ denotes the relational image of s under relation r . The transitive closure operator makes FORL more expressive than First-Order Logic. A FORL specification is a collection of typed variables accompanied by a collection of formulas. Given a specification S we denote by $dec(S)$ its declaration part, and by $form(S)$ its formula part.

The semantics of FORL is given via a set $Atom$ of uninterpreted atoms. Environments assign values to variables: $env = Var \rightarrow Value$, where the values are sets of tuples of atoms, i.e.: $Value = \bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{N}} 2^{Atom^i}$. Expressions are evaluated by a function $X : Expr \rightarrow Env \rightarrow Value$, taking an expression and an environment and returning the corresponding value. Formulas are interpreted via a function $M : Form \rightarrow Env \rightarrow Bool$. For instance, the semantics of the (less standard) relational join is as follows:

$$M(R.T)(e) = \{ \langle a_0, \dots, a_{n-1}, b_1, \dots, b_m \rangle \mid \langle a_0, \dots, a_n \rangle \in R \wedge \langle a_n, b_1, \dots, b_m \rangle \in T \}$$

The semantics of the other operators is standard [5].

Given an environment e , we say that $e \models S$ iff $M(form(S))(e) = true$, and we say that $S \models \phi$, if for every environment e , we have that $e \models S$ implies $e \models \phi$. When useful we use the symbol \oplus for conjoining a formula to a specification, i.e., given a specification S and a formula ϕ (whose free variables are declared in S) then $S \oplus \phi$ is the specification S plus the formula ϕ in its formula part.

LTL and FORL. Sound translations from LTL to FORL are shown in [24, 25]. This allows us to perform LTL model checking on the candidate implementations, by translating both a formula and a transition system to a FORL specification. Precisely, given a transition structure TS and an LTL formula ϕ , we denote by $\mathcal{A}(TS, \phi)$ to the FORL specification, such that, $TS \models \phi$ iff $e \models \mathcal{A}(TS, \phi)$ (for some environment e). Furthermore, an approach to perform bounded model checking over LTL via FORL is introduced in [26].

Guarded-Command Programs. We describe programs using a guarded -command notation [27, 28]. A program consists of a collection of shared variables plus a collection of processes running concurrently in an asynchronous way. Each process has a collection of local variables, an initialization condition, and a set of guarded actions of the style: $[a]B \rightarrow C$ where: a is the name of

the action, B (called the guard) is a boolean statement over the (shared and local) variables of the program, and C is a collection of assignments, written $x_0:=E_0, \dots, x_n:=E_n$. We assume that the test of B and the assignments in C are all executed atomically. Fig.1 shows a simple example of a concurrent program composed of two processes running concurrently.

The operational semantics of this programming notation is simple. A state is an assignment of values to the variables in the program. An action $B \rightarrow C$ is enabled in a state, if B is true in that state. An execution of P is a sequence of states satisfying the following conditions: (i) the initial state satisfies the initial conditions, (ii) if state s_i follows from s_{i-1} in the sequence, then we have some action $B \rightarrow C$ such that B holds at s_{i-1} and executing C results in s_i , (iii) the sequence is infinite (we assume that when no action is enabled then the last state is repeated). The set of all the executions of program P is denoted $Tr(P)$. We say that $P \models \phi$, for a LTL formula ϕ if the executions of the program satisfy ϕ . As shown in [10], guarded-command programs can be mechanically translated to JAVA programs. The following mathematical notation will be used in the rest of this paper: $(x_0, \dots, x_n) \uparrow i$ denotes the i -th projection of the given tuple, $[0, k]$ denotes the set $\{0, \dots, k\}$, and $\prod_{i \in I} S_i$ denotes the cartesian product of sets S_i .

4 Our Model of Concurrency

We consider finite-state concurrent programs of the form $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k$ consisting of a finite collection of processes or threads running in parallel, which communicate with each other via shared variables. We use *try-locks* (i.e., non-blocking locks [1]) as the main synchronization mechanism. Try-locks allow for a fine-grained concurrency. Furthermore, we assume that locks are used to protect shared variables, and then variables can only be written by the processes “owning” the corresponding locks. This is a common practice in languages like JAVA, where *synchronize* clauses and locks are used to provide process synchronization.

Formally, a process with shared variables Sh and locks \mathcal{L} will be modeled as a transition system $P = \langle S, Act, \rightarrow, s, AP, L \rangle$, where $Act = Int \cup Env$, $AP = Sh \cup Loc \cup \mathcal{L}$, and $Sh, Loc, \mathcal{L}, Int, Env$ are mutually disjoint finite sets. Intuitively, Sh is the collection of shared variables available to the process, Loc is the collection of the local variables of the process, \mathcal{L} is the set of locks used by the process, Int is a set of internal actions and Env is a set of environmental actions. From now on, we assume that every shared variable g has a corresponding lock (named ℓ_g), and therefore we have that $\{\ell_g \mid g \in Sh\} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$.

The environmental actions are defined taking into account the shared variables and the locks, i.e.: $Env = \bigcup_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} \{ch_\ell\} \cup \bigcup_{g \in Sh} \{ch_g\} \cup \{env\}$. Intuitively, ch_ℓ is an environmental action that performs changes on lock ℓ , and ch_g is similar but for shared variables. The additional action env represents the possible changes that the environment may perform over the shared variables not owned by the current process.

For the sake of simplicity, we write $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ instead of $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ when $a \in Env$, and we write $s \dashrightarrow s'$ if $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ for some a .

We impose the following restrictions on processes to ensure that they behave according to our model of concurrency:

- P1. $\bigwedge_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (\forall s \in S : av_\ell \notin L(s) \Rightarrow \neg(\exists s' : s \rightarrow s' \wedge own_\ell \in L(s')))$
P2. $\bigwedge_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (\forall s, s' \in S : s \rightarrow s' \wedge own_\ell \notin L(s) \wedge own_\ell \in L(s') \Rightarrow \bigwedge_{\ell' \in \mathcal{L} \setminus \{\ell\}} (own_{\ell'} \in L(s) \equiv own_{\ell'} \in L(s')))$
P3. $\bigwedge_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (\forall s \in S : own_\ell \in L(s) \Rightarrow av_\ell \notin L(s))$
P4. $\bigwedge_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (\forall s \in S : own_\ell \notin L(s) \Rightarrow \exists s' \in S : s \xrightarrow{ch_\ell} s')$
P5. $\bigwedge_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (\forall s, s' \in S : s \xrightarrow{ch_\ell} s' \Rightarrow av_\ell \in L(s) \equiv av_\ell \notin L(s'))$
P6. $\bigwedge_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (\forall s, s' \in S : s \xrightarrow{ch_\ell} s' \Rightarrow \bigwedge_{x \in Sh \cup Loc \setminus \{ch_\ell, av_\ell\}} (x \in L(s) \equiv x \in L(s')))$
P7. $\bigwedge_{g \in Sh} (\forall s, s' \in S : s \xrightarrow{ch_g} s' \Rightarrow \bigwedge_{x \in (Sh \cup Loc) \setminus \{g\}} (x \in L(s) \equiv x \in L(s')))$
P8. $\bigwedge_{g \in Sh} (\forall s \in S : own_{\ell_g} \notin L(s) \wedge av_{\ell_g} \notin L(s) \Rightarrow (\exists s' : s \xrightarrow{ch_g} s' : g \in L(s')) \wedge (\exists s' : s \xrightarrow{ch_g} s' : g \notin L(s')))$
P9. $env = (\bigcup_{g \in Sh} \{ch_g\})^+$

Intuitively, P1 states that, if a lock is not available, then it cannot be acquired. P2 says that only one lock per time unit can be acquired by the process. P3 says that, if a lock is owned by the process, then it is not available. P4 states that, if the process does not own a lock, then the environment can acquire it. P5 expresses the fact that action ch_ℓ changes the state of the lock. P6 states that the environmental action ch_ℓ produces changes only in variables own_ℓ and av_ℓ . P7 is similar but for shared variables. P8 says that, if the lock corresponding to a variable is not owned by the process, then any behavior of the environment is possible. Finally, P9 states that env models the possible changes that the environment may perform over shared variables. This condition makes it possible to promote local properties to the global system (Theorem 1 below).

Note that P8-P9 are similar to the assumptions made in [4] for the synthesis of reactive controllers over open systems. Here, we restricted ourselves to boolean variables, other datatypes can be dealt with in a similar way.

Let us define the transition structure corresponding to the concurrent execution of a collection of processes.

Definition 1. *Given processes P_0, \dots, P_k where $P_i = \langle S_i, Env_i \cup Int_i, Sh \cup Loc_i \cup \mathcal{L}, \rightarrow_i, s_i, L_i \rangle$ for $i \in [0, k]$ with shared variables Sh and locks \mathcal{L} , with $Loc_i, Loc_j, Act_i, Act_j$ being pairwise disjoint for $i \neq j$, we define the structure $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n = \langle S^\parallel, Act^\parallel, \rightarrow^\parallel, s^\parallel, AP^\parallel, L^\parallel, \rangle$ as follows:*

1. $S^\parallel = \{s \in \prod_{i \in [0, k]} S_i \mid \forall g \in Sh : \forall i, j \in [0, k] : L_i(s \uparrow i)(g) = L_j(s \uparrow j)(g)\} \cap \{s \in \prod_{i \in [0, k]} S_i \mid \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L} : \#\{i \in [0, k] \mid L_i(s \uparrow i)(own_\ell)\} \leq 1\}$,
2. $Act^\parallel = \bigcup_{i \in [0, k]} Act_i$,
3. $\rightarrow^\parallel = \{(s, a, s') \mid \exists i \in [0, k] : ((s \uparrow i \xrightarrow{a} s' \uparrow i) \wedge (\forall j \neq i : s \uparrow j = s' \uparrow j))\}$,
4. $s^\parallel = \langle s_0, \dots, s_k \rangle$,
5. $AP^\parallel = ((Sh \cup \bigcup_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}, i \in [0, k]} \{own_\ell^i, av_\ell^i\}) \setminus \bigcup_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} \{own_\ell, av_\ell\}) \cup \bigcup_{i \in [0, k]} Loc_i$,
6. $L^\parallel(s)(x) = L_0(s \uparrow 0)(x)$ if $x \in Sh \setminus \{own_\ell, av_\ell\}$,

7. $L^{\parallel}(s)(x) = L_i(s\uparrow i)(x)$ if $x \in Loc_i$,
8. $L^{\parallel}(s)(own_\ell^i) = L_i(s\uparrow i)(own_\ell)$,
9. $L^{\parallel}(s)(av_\ell^i) = L_i(s\uparrow i)(av_\ell)$.

Roughly speaking, the global system is an asynchronous product of the participating processes, where the valuation of shared variables coincides for every process, and each lock is mapped to its owner. It is easy to see that this construction suffers from the state explosion problem, thus the explicit construction of this structure is unfeasible in practice.

One interesting point about our formalization is that certain properties can be promoted from a given process to the concurrent program where this process resides, this enables modular reasoning over asynchronous products.

Theorem 1. *Given processes P_0, \dots, P_k such that $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k$ is well formed and a LTL-X property ϕ , if $P_i \models \phi$, then we have: $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n \models_{\mathcal{F}} \phi$.*

Note that local properties are preserved only by fair executions, otherwise one could devise some global execution that prevents the process from progressing.

4.1 Obtaining Guarded-Command Programs.

Interestingly, given a structure $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k$ we can define a corresponding program in the guarded-command notation, written $Prog(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k)$, as follows. The shared variables are those in Sh plus an additional shared variable ℓ for each lock, with domain $[0, k] \cup \{\perp\}$ (where \perp is a value used to indicate that the lock is available). Additionally, for each $\langle S_i, Env_i \cup Int_i, Sh \cup Loc_i \cup \mathcal{L}, \rightarrow_i, s_i, L_i \rangle$ we define a corresponding process. To do so, we introduce for each $s \in S_i$ the equivalence class: $[s] = \{s' \in S_i \mid (s \dashrightarrow^* s') \vee (s' \dashrightarrow^* s)\}$. That is, it is the set of states connected to s via environmental transitions. It is direct to prove that it is already an equivalence class. The collection of all equivalence classes is denoted S_i / \dashrightarrow^* . The local variables of the process are those in Loc_i . Additionally, a fresh variable $state$, with domain S_i / \dashrightarrow^* , is considered. It is worth noting that the programs we synthesize follow the discipline of acquiring a lock before modifying the corresponding variable. When a lock is not available, the process may continue executing other branches. However, note that a process could get blocked when all its guards are false, thus other synchronization mechanisms such as blocking locks, semaphores and condition variables can be expressed by these programs. Finally, given states $s, s' \in S_i$ with $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ and $[s] \neq [s']$, we consider the following guarded command:

$$[a] \left(\begin{array}{l} state = [s] \\ \wedge \wedge \{x = (x \in L(s)) \mid x \in Sh \cup Loc\} \\ \wedge \wedge \{\ell = i \mid \ell \in \mathcal{L} : own_\ell \in L(s)\} \\ \wedge \wedge \{\ell = \perp \mid \ell \in \mathcal{L} : av_\ell \in L(s)\} \end{array} \right) \rightarrow \left(\begin{array}{l} \{x := x \in L(s') \mid x \in Loc \cup Sh\} \\ \cup \{state := [s']\} \\ \cup \{\ell := i \mid \ell \in \mathcal{L} : own_\ell \in L(s)\} \\ \cup \{\ell := \perp \mid \ell \in \mathcal{L} : av_\ell \in L(s)\} \end{array} \right)$$

We can prove that our translation from transition systems to programs is correct. That is, the executions of the program satisfy the same temporal properties as the asynchronous product $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n$.

Fig. 1: Transition Structure and Program with a lock m for Mutex

Theorem 2. *Given a program $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n$ and LTL property ϕ , then we have that: $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n \models \phi \Leftrightarrow \text{Prog}(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n) \models \phi$*

Example 1 (Mutex). Consider a system composed of two processes (it can straightforwardly be generalized to n processes) both with non-critical, waiting and critical sections. The global property is mutual exclusion: the two processes cannot be in their critical sections simultaneously. We consider one lock ℓ , actions: *getNCS* (the process enters to the non-critical section), *getCS* (the process enters to the critical section), *getLock* (the process acquires the lock), *getTry* (the process goes to the try state), and the corresponding propositions $ncs, cs, try, own_\ell, av_\ell$.

In Fig. 1 the transition system and the program corresponding to this example are shown. It is interesting to observe that, the coherence conditions P1-P9 imply that, for any action $B \rightarrow C$ containing a $x := E$ in C for a shared variable x , we have that the statement $\ell_x = i$ is implied by B (if $x := E$ is different from the skip statement), i.e., the lock corresponding to x is acquired by the process before executing the assignment. Similarly, note that locks are acquired only if they are available.

4.2 Defining Processes in FORL.

Given a process as defined above, we can easily describe it in FORL. A type *Node* is used for modeling the states, the transition relation is described using binary relations, propositions are captured using a type *Prop*, and the valuation function is defined via a relation $val : Node \rightarrow Prop$. Finally, formulas are used to describe the transitions. Let us describe this by means of an example. Consider the process of Fig.1, the corresponding FORL specification is shown in Fig.2. Note that we use variables *succs* and *env* to capture the relations \rightarrow and \dashrightarrow , respectively. Given a transition structure TS we call $\mathcal{A}(TS)$ its corresponding specification. Note that, if we replace $getTry = \{(s_5, s_3), (s_2, s_4)\}$ by $getTry \subseteq \{(s_5, s_3), (s_2, s_4)\}$ in the given specification, we obtain a weaker specification. Performing this for all the internal actions returns a specification which, intuitively, allows the SAT solver to disable some local transitions, thus the non-determinism may be reduced. This weaker theory is denoted by $\mathcal{A}_{Ref}(TS)$.

```

succs, local, env : Node × Node
val : Node × Prop
s0, s1, s2, s3, s4, s5 : Node
val = {(s5, ncsi), (s5, avm), (s2, ncsi), (s4, tryi), (s3, tryi), (s3, avm),
      (s1, tryi), (s1, ownm), (s0, csi), (s0, ownm)}
getTry = {(s5, s3), (s2, s4)}
getNCS = {s0, s5}
getCS = {(s1, s0)}
getLock = {(s3, s1), (s3, s3), (s4, s4)}
chℓ = {(s3, s4), (s4, s3), (s5, s2), (s2, s5)}
local = getTry ∪ getNCS ∪ getCS ∪ getLock

```

Fig. 2: FORL specification for Mutex

4.3 Specifying Distributed Programs

Distributed programs are specified by means of a collection of FORL specifications that share some symbols (locks and shared variables) plus a global temporal property.

Definition 2. *A specification of a distributed program is a tuple: $\langle Sh, \mathcal{L}, \{S_i\}_{i \in I}, \phi \rangle$ where $Sh = \{g_0, \dots, g_p\}$ is a finite collection of shared variable names, $\mathcal{L} = \{\ell_0, \dots, \ell_q\} \cup \{\ell_{g_i} \mid 0 \leq i \leq p\}$ is a finite collection of lock names including names for the shared variables and I is a finite index set. Furthermore, each specification S_i contains in its declaration part:*

- Types $Node, Prop$ characterising the process' states, and the set of propositions, respectively.
- Variables $init:Node$ and $p, q, \dots:Prop$ characterizing the initial state and the propositions, respectively,
- Relations $a_0, \dots, a_m:Node \rightarrow Node$ and $ch_{g_0}, \dots, ch_{g_p}:Node \rightarrow Node$, representing the internal actions, and the environmental actions, respectively.
- Relations $p_0, \dots, p_t:Node \rightarrow Prop$ corresponding to the local variables, and $ch_{g_0}, \dots, ch_{g_p}:Node \rightarrow Node$ corresponding to the shared variables,
- Relations $\{av_\ell \mid \ell \in \mathcal{L}\} \cup \{own_\ell \mid \ell \in \mathcal{L}\}$ of type $Node \rightarrow Prop$ representing the lock mechanisms associated to the shared variables.

S_i contains axioms P1-P9. Furthermore, ϕ is a LTL-X formula containing propositional variables declared in the S_i 's.

Given a program specification $\langle Sh, \mathcal{L}, \{S_i\}, \phi \rangle$, an instance of it is a collection of environments $\{e_i\}_{i \in I}$ such that: $e_i \models S_i$. Furthermore, let TS_{e_i} be the transition structure corresponding to e_i , then we have $TS_{e_0} \parallel \dots \parallel TS_{e_k} \models \phi$. Typically, a process specification contains axioms for the actions in the style of pre and postconditions, plus frame axioms (i.e., the list of variables that are not changed by the actions), in addition to axioms P1-P9.

Example 2 (Mutex cont.). Let us consider a specification for the mutex example with two processes. The specification is given by a tuple $\langle \emptyset, \{m\}, \{S_0, S_1\}, \phi \rangle$

where there is no shared variables, a lock m , specifications S_0 and S_1 corresponding to the two processes, whose variable declarations are those in Example 1. The formulas of the specification define the actions in terms of pre and postconditions, e.g.:

$$\forall s, s' : Node \mid s' \in enterCS_i[s] \Rightarrow ((try_i \in val[s]) \wedge (own_{m_i} \in val_i[s])) \Rightarrow cs \in val_i[s']$$

states the pre and postcondition of action $enterCS$ (and similarly for the other actions). The global property ϕ is *mutual exclusion*, which can be easily characterised in LTL.

5 Algorithms for Synthesis

A basic synthesis procedure consists of two steps: (i) a backtracking search over the space of instances of each process specification; and (ii) the use of a model checker to find those instances not satisfying the global property. We propose an improved version of this basic algorithm that takes advantage of the counterexamples provided by the model checker. Our approach starts by generating instances for each local specification, and then checks, by using model checking, whether the concurrent execution of the processes satisfies the global properties. Particularly, we rely on SAT solving to generate valid instances for the processes and, to verify the validity of the global properties, we use a symbolic model checker (NuSMV [29]). When a counterexample is found, the implementations of the processes involved in the counterexample are refined in order to obtain valid implementations that satisfy the global properties.

A counterexample of $TS_0 \parallel \dots \parallel TS_n \models \phi$ is an execution π of $TS_0 \parallel \dots \parallel TS_n$ such that $\pi \not\models \phi$. Our refinement phase takes a counterexample generated by a model checker, and *projects* this global execution to local executions of the participating processes. As shown below, this information can be used to get rid of the counterexample, and thus, the SAT solving phase can be speed up. In finite transition structures, counterexamples can be represented by finite paths, called *lasso traces* (a finite sequence of states, such that the last state has a loop to some previous state) [30]. Furthermore, note that any finite path can be captured by an FORL formula.

Definition 3. Given $TS = \langle S, \{a_0, \dots, a_n\}, \rightarrow, s, AP, L \rangle$ and a finite path $\pi = s_0 \rightarrow s_1 \rightarrow s_2 \dots \rightarrow s_m$ in TS . The following FORL formula over the vocabulary of $\mathcal{A}(TS)$ captures this path: $CNF(\pi) = \bigwedge_{0 \leq j < m} (\bigvee_{0 \leq i \leq n} (s_{j+1} \in a_i[s_j]))$

Let us denote by $\llbracket CNF(\pi) \rrbracket$ the set of clauses of formula $CNF(\pi)$.

Given processes TS_0, \dots, TS_k , any execution π of $TS_0 \parallel \dots \parallel TS_k$ can be projected to an execution of process TS_i (for each i).

Definition 4. Given a collection TS_0, \dots, TS_k of transition structures and a finite execution $\sigma = s_0 \rightarrow s_1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow s_m$ in the structure $TS_0 \parallel \dots \parallel TS_k$, we denote by $\sigma \uparrow i$ the following path: $s_0 \uparrow i \rightarrow s_1 \uparrow i \rightarrow \dots$

Note that projecting a global execution may introduce stuttering steps in local executions. The projections of a global execution form a tuple $\langle c \uparrow 0, \dots, c \uparrow k \rangle$, that will be used to refine the instances obtained via the SAT solver. Furthermore, we define a relation $c \sqsubseteq c'$ between counterexamples, which intuitively states that c is included in (or refines) c' :

Definition 5. *Given a transition structure TS and finite paths c and c' in TS , then: $c \sqsubseteq c'$ iff $\llbracket \text{CNF}(c) \rrbracket \subseteq \llbracket \text{CNF}(c') \rrbracket$*

It is straightforward to prove that this relation is reflexive, transitive and anti-symmetric. Similarly, we can define a disjointness relation:

Definition 6. *Given a transition structure TS and finite paths c and c' in TS , then: $c * c'$ iff $c \not\sqsubseteq c' \wedge c' \not\sqsubseteq c$.*

When $c * c'$ we say that c and c' are disjoint. The algorithm uses this relationship to improve the search for programs. Suppose that model checking $TS_0 \parallel \dots \parallel TS_k$ returns a counterexample c which can be projected to a tuple of paths $\langle c_0, \dots, c_k \rangle$. Then, each specification $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(TS_i)$ can be enriched with a formula $\text{NOT}(c_i)$ that removes the counterexample c_i from the instances of the specification. This is achieved by requiring that some transitions of the counterexample (not including stuttering steps) must be disabled.

Definition 7. *Given a path $c = s_0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow s_m$, such that $s_i \neq s_{i+1}$ for some i , in a transition structure $TS = \langle S, \{a_0, \dots, a_n\}, \rightarrow, s, AP, L \rangle$, we define the following formula using the variables declared in $\mathcal{A}(TS)$:*

$$\text{NOT}(c) = \bigvee_{0 \leq i < m} (\bigwedge_{0 \leq j \leq n} \neg(s_{i+1} \in a_j[s_i]) \wedge (s_i \neq s_{i+1}))$$

A direct consequence of this definition is that the instances of specification (i.e., possible refinements of the original specification) $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(TS) \oplus \text{NOT}(c)$ do not admit the same execution $c = s_0 \rightarrow s_1 \dots \rightarrow s_m$, that is:

Theorem 3. *Given a path $c = s_0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow s_m$, with $s_i \neq s_{i+1}$ for some i , of a transition structure TS , then: $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(TS) \oplus \text{NOT}(c) \not\models \text{CNF}(c)$.*

The next property of \sqsubseteq follows straightforwardly from Def. 7 and Def. 5.

Theorem 4. *Given paths $c = s_0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow s_m$, with $s_i \neq s_{i+1}$ for some i , and $c' = s'_0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow s'_{m'}$, with $s'_i \neq s'_{i+1}$ for some i , in a transition structure TS , then: If $c \sqsubseteq c'$, then $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(TS) \oplus \text{NOT}(c) \models \text{NOT}(c')$*

This essentially says that formula $\text{NOT}(c)$ rules out not only counterexample c , but also more general counterexamples c' from the possible implementations (it is in this sense that c refines c'). Observe also that, if c and c' are disjoint, then removing counterexample c does not necessarily remove counterexample c' from the model, and vice versa. That is, the two formulas $\text{NOT}(c)$ and $\text{NOT}(c')$ must be considered. We use these properties to refine the algorithm described in the beginning of this section.

The synthesis algorithm is described in Alg. 1.1. Let us give an intuitive explanation of this algorithm. The procedure takes as input an index indicating the specification being processed, the collection of process specifications,

Algorithm 1.1: Counter Example Search

```

1 input:  $i$  process number,  $\{S_0, \dots, S_n\}$  process specifications,  $\phi$  global property,  $k$ 
   instance bound
2 output:  $\{p_0, \dots, p_n\}$  with  $p_0 \parallel \dots \parallel p_n \models \phi$  and  $p_i \models S_i$ , or  $\emptyset$  otherwise
3 procedure SyntCex( $i, S_0, \dots, S_n, \phi, k$ )
4   while  $S_i$  has unprocessed instances do
5      $M[i] \leftarrow$  next instance of  $S_i$ ;  $inCexs_i \leftarrow \emptyset$ ;  $outCexs_i \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
6     while  $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(M[i]) \oplus (\bigwedge_{c \in inCexs_i} \text{NOT}(c)) \oplus form(S_i)$  has unprocessed instances do
7        $r[i] \leftarrow$  next instance of  $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(M[i]) \oplus (\bigwedge_{c \in inCexs_i} \text{NOT}(c)) \oplus form(S_i)$ 
8       if ( $i = n$ ) then
9         if  $r[0] \parallel \dots \parallel r[n] \models \phi$  then return  $\{r[0], \dots, r[n]\}$ 
10        else
11           $cex \leftarrow$  found counterexample
12          if  $\forall c \in gcexs : \exists j \leq n : (c \uparrow j) * (cex \uparrow j)$  then
13             $gcexs \leftarrow gcexs \cup \{cex\}$ ;
14            for all  $i$  such that  $cex \uparrow i \notin outCexs_i$  do
15              Push( $inCexs_i, cex \uparrow i$ );
16            return  $\emptyset$ 
17          endif
18          if  $\forall c \in currentCexs : c * (cex \uparrow n)$  then
19            Push( $inCexs_n, cex \uparrow n$ )
20          for all  $c \in gcexs$  satisfying  $cex \sqsubseteq c$  do
21            Replace( $gcexs, c, cex$ )
22          for all  $i$  do Replace( $inCexs_i, c \uparrow i, cex \uparrow i$ )
23          endfor
24        endif
25      else
26         $found \leftarrow$  SyntCex( $i + 1, s_0, \dots, s_n, \phi, k$ )
27        if  $found \neq \emptyset$  then return  $found$ 
28        if no next instance of  $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(M[i]) \oplus (\bigwedge_{c \in inCexs_i} \text{NOT}(c)) \oplus form(S_i)$ 
29          and  $inCexs_i \neq \emptyset$  then
30           $outCexs_i \leftarrow$  Pop( $inCexs_i$ )
31        endif
32      endwhile
33    endwhile
34    return  $\emptyset$ ;
35 end

```

the global property, a bound on the number of states of the processes to be synthesized. It performs a backtracking search over all the process instances for each specification. A collection $gcexs$ is used to keep track of the found counterexamples. The loop of line 4 inspects all the instances of specification number i . For each instance $M[i]$ obtained via the SAT solver we use two auxiliary sets: $inCexs_i$ that keeps track of the projections of the counterexamples found when dealing with the actual instance (it behaves in a stack-like way); and $outCexs_i$ that is used to save the counterexamples that were (unsuccessfully) taken into account during the iterations. Then, all the instances of theory $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(M[i]) \oplus (\bigwedge_{c \in inCexs_i} \text{NOT}(c)) \oplus form(S_i)$ are inspected in the loop of line 6. In the first iteration, $\bigwedge_{c \in inCexs_i} \text{NOT}(c) = true$, since $inCexs_i$ is empty. Also note that we add $form(S_i)$ to the theory to be solved, this is because some of the refinements may prune too much non-determinism in such a way that some of the axioms of S_i may be falsified. In practice, the specification $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(M[i])$ describes part of its possible instances, and so it is usually faster to get instances from this than to get instances from S_i . In line 27, the procedure calls itself recursively until the last specification is reached ($i = n$). Then, the algorithm checks

if the instances obtained for each process (r_0, \dots, r_n) satisfy the global property, returning a valid program, or adding the found counterexample to the set of counterexamples, before continuing with the search. This approach improves the previously introduced basic algorithm in three ways: if a counterexample refining some counterexample in $gcexs$ is found (lines 20-23), the latter is changed by the former (that is, we refine the set of counterexamples) and we continue the search with the refined counterexample (the procedure $Replace(S, x, y)$ replaces x by y in set S); if a disjoint counterexample is found we restart the search adding the new counterexamples to the $inCexs_i$ for every i (lines 12-17). A particular case arises when the found counterexample is only disjoint with the actual one, in which case we add the corresponding counterexample to $inCexs_n$ and continue with the search. For the other specifications (that is, $i < n$), if no program was found then either new counterexamples were added to $inCexs_i$, in which case the SAT solver will search instances over a refined specification (line 6), or no more counterexamples were added to $inCexs_i$ and the stack will be popped. The idea of the stack is to strengthen the specification to speed up the process of finding an instance.

Soundness, Termination and Bounded-Completeness. The soundness of this algorithm is direct, since a model checker is used to verify the output. Termination is less straightforward, the loop of line 4 finalizes because the number of instances of size k for any specification is finite. The loop of line 6 is also executed a finite number of times: if $i = n$, the theory $\mathcal{A}_{ref}(M[i]) \oplus (\bigwedge_{c \in inCexs_i} \text{NOT}(c)) \oplus form(S_i)$ has a finite number of instances, but note that the set $inCexs_i$ could be increased (line 15), but since FORL is a monotonic logic, the number of instances is decremented when more counterexamples are considered, that is, eventually we will reach an inconsistent specification or all the instances will be processed and the algorithm will exit the loop. For $i < n$, the set $inCexs_i$ is updated in a similar way, but when an inconsistent specification is generated (line 28) we start popping counterexamples from the stack. In this case, we go back to a specification that has been dealt with before, and then we will get the next instance that was not still processed for this theory, at some point all the instances will be generated and the loop will terminate.

For the bounded completeness, suppose that there are instances r_0, \dots, r_n of size k such that $r_0, \dots, r_n \models \phi$. Note that in line 6 all the instances for each i are generated, afterwards the algorithm starts inspecting the refinements of each instance, including itself. As remarked above, the loop of line 6 will terminate because it eventually starts to pop elements from the stack, and therefore the next instance of specification i will be obtained. Summing up (in the worst case) all the combinations of instances of the specifications will be checked by the model checker, and then the algorithm will find the sequence r_0, \dots, r_n .

6 Experiments

We have implemented a prototype of the algorithm, available in [31]. The tool takes as input a program specification and returns, when possible, an implemen-

Table 1: Experimental Results

Example	L.Scope	L.Time	T.Time	Its.	Result
Mutex(2)	<6	1.31s	1.76s	-	UNSAT
Mutex(2)	6	1.32s	1.75s	1	SAT
Mutex(3)	6	1.15s	1.59s	1	SAT
Mutex(4)	6	1.15s	1.54s	1	SAT
Mutex(5)	6	1.46s	2.39s	1	SAT
Mutex(6)	6	1.1s	1.78s	1	SAT
Mutex(7)	6	1.12s	1.56s	1	SAT
Mutex(8)	6	1.2s	1.71s	1	SAT
Phil(2)	<14	26.64s	27.1s	-	UNSAT
Phil(3)	14	2.23s	4.25s	4	SAT
Phil(4)	14	2.27s	4.71s	4	SAT
Phil(5)	14	2.29s	9.35s	4	SAT
Phil(6)	14	2.18s	24.68s	4	SAT
Phil(7)	14	2.13s	1m37s	4	SAT
Phil(8)	14	2.18s	7m35s	4	SAT
RW(1,1)	<8	1.88s	2.81s	-	UNSAT
RW(1,1)	8	1.42s	1.9s	1	SAT
RW(2,3)	16	12.44s	13s	1	SAT
RW(2,6)	16	12.61s	13.2s	1	SAT
RW(3,3)	<17	1m14s	1m15s	-	UNSAT
Peterson(2)	<12	6.6s	6.9s	-	UNSAT
Peterson(2)	12	6.71s	7.82s	6	SAT
Peterson(3)	<16	9m45s	9m49s	-	UNSAT
Barrier(2)	<16	9m52s	9m54s	-	UNSAT
Barrier(2)	16	9.68s	11.12s	8	SAT
Barrier(3)	<17	8m57s	8m59s	-	UNSAT

tation in the guarded command language of Section 3, which is directly translatable to any modern programming language. We have evaluated the tool with five standard examples of distributed algorithms: Mutex (see Figure 1), Dining Philosophers [32], Readers and Writers [2], Peterson’s algorithm for mutual exclusion [2] and a Barrier protocol [33]. Table 1 summarizes the obtained experimental results. The experiments were conducted on an Intel i5 3.00GHz processor with 8GB of memory, running Ubuntu 16.04 and JAVA 1.8. Table 1 shows the bound over the size of the processes (L.Scope), the maximum time needed to generate local process instances (L.Time), the total time required for synthesizing the system (T.Time), the number of times that the model checker was invoked (Its) by the synthesizer, and the result returned by the model checker, SAT if a program was returned, UNSAT otherwise.

Particularly, $\text{Mutex}(k)$ indicates that we consider k concurrent processes in the mutex example. Similarly for Peterson’s algorithm and the Barrier protocol. $\text{RW}(n,m)$ denotes that n readers and m writers were considered. Rows with

entries $< k$ show the maximum time spent by the tool when the bound was less than k .

The tool was able to find several different solutions for the examples, for instance, for the philosophers, the first solution found (reported in Table 1) is one in which each philosopher takes a fork only when her two forks are available; this is a distributed solution that prevents the occurrence of deadlocks. Another solution found by the tool is the even/odd solution where $n - 1$ philosophers take first their left fork and after their right fork, whereas the philosopher n takes first her right fork and then her left fork. As it can be observed in the table, while one increment the number of processes, the number of locks also is incremented (global variables), so then the time required by our tool to find candidate solutions, and verifying its validity, is incremented as well.

Precisely, Table 1 shows that the technique scales well for those case studies in which each process only uses a reduced number of locks or shared variables (e.g. the dining philosophers, mutex and reader-writers). However, for those examples where the number of shared variables accessed by the processes is bigger (e.g., the barrier protocol), the technique does not scale that well. Intuitively, more shared variables imply more actions performed by the environment, which increases the size of the formula fed to the SAT solver. As future work, we plan to investigate the possibility of equipping our specifications with assumptions over the behavior of the environment, in order to restrict the possible values of shared variables, this could simplify the SAT problem when searching for local implementations.

7 Final Remarks

The development of correct synchronization skeletons for concurrent programs is a very difficult, and error prone, activity, since subtle mistakes may introduce common concurrency errors, e.g., deadlocks. In this work, we presented a correct-by-construction approach for the synthesis of synchronization skeletons, from FORL specifications, for concurrent programs. Our approach iteratively generates candidate process implementations by using SAT solving, and manipulates the found counterexamples to extract valuable information to refine the search. In contrast to previous works, our approach performs a local reasoning to avoid the explicit construction of the global state space, and applies to general temporal properties, namely, safety and liveness. Our approach is correct and complete, under a given bound on the size of the process implementations. We developed a prototype tool that effectively solved common examples of distributed algorithms. Due to its efficiency is affected while the number of global locks is incremented, we plan to extend our approach, by equipping our specifications with assumptions to restrict the environment behaviour, in order to simplify the SAT problem generated, and reduce the number of instances to be explored by the solvers.

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Appendix

Proof of Theorem 1 First, we prove that for any trace $\pi' \in Tr(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k)(s)$ we have that the projection of this trace to process P_i is stutter equivalent to some trace $\pi \in Tr(P_i)(s\uparrow i)$. Since stutter equivalence preserves LTL-X properties, the result follows.

Let $\pi' \in Tr(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k)(s)$, then we prove that the trace $\pi\uparrow i = \pi[0]\uparrow i \rightarrow \pi[1]\uparrow i \rightarrow \dots$ is stutter equivalent to a trace $\pi \in Tr(P_i)(s\uparrow i)$. π is just defined by removing all the transitions in $\pi[j]\uparrow i \rightarrow \pi[j+1]\uparrow i$ that do not correspond to transitions in P_i , it is simple to see that the removed transitions are stuttering steps, that is $L_i(\pi[j]\uparrow i) = L_i(\pi[j+1]\uparrow i)$, otherwise if $L_i(\pi[j]\uparrow i) \neq L_i(\pi[j+1]\uparrow i)$ the transition must correspond to the transition of another process (say P_j). Furthermore, $L_i(\pi[j]\uparrow i)$ and $L_i(\pi[j+1]\uparrow i)$ can only differ on their valuation of shared variables (they must coincide on the valuation of Int_i), but by the condition **P7** we have a matching transition in P_i which is a contradiction. Also note that removing these transitions keeps the trace infinite, since π is fair. Since we have removed only stuttering steps, the resulting execution is stutter equivalent to $\pi\uparrow i$. Now, given any LTL-X property ϕ then suppose that $P_i \models \phi$ and $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k \not\models \phi$, that is, we have some $\pi \in Tr(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k)(s)$ such that $\pi \not\models \phi$ but since all the propositional variables in ϕ are in $Sh \cup Loc_i$ we have that $\pi\uparrow i \not\models \phi$, and by the property described above, we have a $\pi' \in Tr(P_i)(s\uparrow i)$ such that $\pi' \not\models \phi$ which is a contradiction, and so $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k \models \phi$.

Proof of Theorem 2 Given a program $P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n$, we have an one-to-one function $f : Tr(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n) \rightarrow Tr(Prog(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n))$, such that, for every $\pi \in Tr(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_n)$ and $i \geq 0$ we have that: $\pi[i] \models \phi$ iff $f(\pi)[i] \models \theta(\phi)$, being ϕ any boolean formula. Let us define for each $\pi \in Tr(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k)$ a corresponding execution $f(\pi) \in Tr(Prog(P_0 \parallel \dots \parallel P_k))$. The definition of $f(\pi)$ is by induction, for $pi[0]$ the corresponding state is the initial state of the program, which by definition satisfies the same boolean formulas. Now, assume that $f(\pi[0]) \dots f(\pi[n])$ are defined, and consider $pi[n+1]$, we know that there is a transition $\pi[i] \xrightarrow[\alpha]{} [i+1]$, then by definition of the asynchronous product we have a process P_j with a transition $\pi[i]\uparrow j \rightarrow \pi[i+1]\uparrow j$, if $[\pi[i]] = [\pi[i+1]]$ then we define $f(\pi[i+1]) = f(\pi[i])$, otherwise we have a corresponding guarded command $B \rightarrow C$ in the process corresponding to P_j such that, by induction, $f(\pi[i]) \models B$ and we define $f(\pi[i+1])$ the state obtained after executing C , which by definition of the program satisfies the same boolean properties as $\pi[i+1]$. This finishes the proof.